

SPORTS COMMUNICATION AS A SOCIAL PHENOMENON

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11197518>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the problem of communication in sports. It is given patterns of connection between sportsmen and a coach in order to exchange information and emotions. And then sports can bring positive results to one's physical and psychological health

Key-words: team, coach, intergroup, socialization, cognitive, verbal, non-verbal, mental health

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена проблеме коммуникации в спорте. Даны схемы связи между спортсменами и тренером для обмена информацией и эмоциями. Так как занятия спортом могут принести положительные результаты для физического и психологического здоровья человека

Ключевые слова: команда, тренер, межгруппа, социализация, когнитивные, вербальные, невербальные, психическое здоровье

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola sportdagi kommunikatsiya masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Ma'lumot va his-tuyg'ularni almashish uchun sportchilar hamda murabbiylar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning o'ziga xosligi berilgan. Chunki sport bilan shug'ullanish insonning jismoniy va psixologik salomatligi uchun ijobiy natijalar berishi lozim

Kalit so'zlar: jamoa, murabbiy, guruhlararo, ijtimoiylashuv, kognitiv, verbal, noverbal, ruhiy salomatlik

Sports communication is an aspect of [communication studies](#) which specializes in the study of communication in a sports setting. It can encompass the study of interpersonal and organizational communication (both verbal and [non-verbal](#)) between participants within a particular [sport](#) (e.g. players, [coaches](#), managers, [referees](#), trainers and physiotherapists, and governing bodies); communication between sports participants, fans, and the media; and the way that sports are represented and communicated in the media. Sports communication is something that happens at different levels ranging from preschool to college level. It's not restricted to professionals. It happens constantly and works best with people that are willing to work well as a team. If everyone is on board and has positive thoughts and communication, it becomes very dismantling to the person receiving the message. It is not only for positive talk, though, because negative sports communication happens all the time. The specificity of communication, in contrast to other types of communication is the occurrence of psychological contact between communicating.

Communication is the art of successfully sharing meaningful information with people using an interchange of experience [1]. Coaches wish to motivate the athletes they work with and to provide them with information that will allow them to train effectively and improve performance. Teams that promote positive communication and respect among players

improve overall motivation. Coaches who learn to communicate effectively with their sportsmen can deliver positive feedback and constructive criticism in ways that actually influence players' performance.

In this study, an attempt is made to carefully analyze the meaning of the semantic concept of communication, its manifestations, which occupy an important place in improving interpersonal relationships. The aim of the study is a theoretical and philosophical analysis of the nature, content and significance of the problem of sports communication. Research objectives include the following:

- comparative study of scientific and theoretical literature devoted to this problem,
- disclosure of social determinants of the concept of sports communication,
- analysis of factors influencing to sports communication,
- study of the genesis of sports communication, as well as its development.

In carrying out this research work, we used following **methods**: structural-functional, causal analysis, dialectic and integrated approach, logic, historicity, consistency, objectivity, continuity, comparison, as well as new scientific installations of the synergetic method.

The object of research is the problems of sports communication. The subject of the study is the effective influence of communication on the formation of a harmoniously developed personality of sportsman.

Communication can be direct and indirect. Three types of communication are distinguished depending on the number of people communicating:

1. Interpersonal (coach — sportsman)
2. Individual group (coach — team)
3. Intergroup (between teams)

Personal-group communication is often used to train sportsmen, and interpersonal communication is for educational purposes. If the goals of communication coincide, then interaction occurs; if the goals are mutually exclusive, then communication takes on the form of confrontation. In interpersonal communication, which applies only to communicating, the position of each of them is reflected. If the communication participants are representatives of groups, collectives, then they are not completely free in their positions and methods of contact, because they care about the prestige of the groups they represent. Therefore, carrying out educational work by the coach with a student belonging to a company with asocial behavior is difficult, especially if communication is carried out in the presence of other guys from this company [2].

Communication can be short and long. Long-term communication makes it possible to better understand each other, but at the same time it can lead to mutual saturation, which is often observed among sportsmen who are at a training camp for a long time.

By direction, communication is classified as follows:

- 1) socially-oriented communication - referrals to partners, to the whole team as a whole;
- 2) personality-oriented communication - appeal to individual partners, team members;
- 3) subtextual orientation - an appeal to a specific sportsman or group is actually addressed to a completely different sportsman.

In accordance with the content of communication, the following communication functions are distinguished:

- 1) cognitive - transfer of knowledge and skills by a coach to sportsmen
- 2) expressive - understanding of each other's experiences and emotional state

3) regulatory - the impact of the coach on the sportsman with the aim of changing or maintaining his behavior, nature of activity, etc.

4) social control - regulation of the activities of sportsmen through praise or censure;

5) socialization - the formation of sportsmen collectivist attitudes, patriotism, etc [2].

Communication tools are divided into two groups: verbal and non-verbal. Verbal communication is the main both in frequency of use and in content [4]. With the help of speech, the coach gives orders, explains, evaluates the behavior and actions of his students, regulates their condition, and game sportsmen tell each other during the game what actions should be taken to make the interaction effective.

Competitive gaming sports activities are characterized by the use of short speech messages, which include:

- pronouncing the name of the partner in order to attract his attention, to indicate a certain combination, to encourage the partner to act in a certain way;
- the short name of the combination when planning actions ("cross", "wedge", "shift");
- a message about the alleged actions - yours or your partner's: "me", "you", "right behind me", etc . ;
- a message about your or partner's location ("here", "go out", "go to the sixth");
- indications of the partner's desired actions: "insure", "higher" (on passing the ball in volleyball), "take it" (on joint protective actions in football), etc . ;
- Evaluation of the actions of one or one's partner: "well done" , "sorry, I was mistaken" ;
- an impulse to activity: "come on, come on", "have taken", etc.

Non-verbal communication are widely used in sports, since in a number of sports speech communication is either absent or limited. For example, it is almost absent in sports with direct contact between rivals.

Nowadays the communication of the coach with sportsmen is second only to the communication of sportsmen with family members .It is through him that learning, the transfer of knowledge, and the education of students occur. Therefore, the coach should pay great attention to the process of communication.

Of particular importance is the communication of the coach with the team in a game of sports. It should be continuous, it is necessary to apply whenever possible to each player, because otherwise, some sportsmen will think that the coach ignores them. Violation of intra-group communication leads, as a rule, to disruption of game interaction, and sometimes conflicts between players.

The coach's communication with the team takes the form of tips during the game, instructions for replacing players, clarifications and beliefs during timeouts [5]. However, it is important to choose the right moment for one form or another of your intervention. The coach must not only be able to communicate with sportsmen, but also require intra-group communication from his sportsmen during the game. Communication efficiency is determined by many factors. Communication factors include: the situation in which communication takes place, the communication environment, the personality of the sportsman and the socio-psychological characteristics of the sports team, the attitude of students to the coach[3]. Some of them are controllable and, therefore, can be specially designed by the body so that the goal of communication is achieved with the greatest probability; others are uncontrollable, at least at the time of communication, and therefore should only be taken into account by the coach when building communication strategies and tactics.

Sports communication depend on mental skills of coach and sportsman. The mental training is to assist sport participants in the development of mental skills to achieve performance success and personal well-being. A model of mental skills for sportsmen and coaches includes four basic types of mental skills in sport:

1. Foundations skills are individual resources that are the basic foundation mental skills necessary to achieve success in sport: achievement drive, self-awareness, productive thinking, self-confidence;
2. Performance skills are psychological abilities critical to the execution of athletic skills during sport performance: perceptual-cognitive skill, attentional focus, energy management;
3. Personal development skills are maturational features of personal development which allow for high-level psychological functioning through clarity of self-concept, feelings of well-being, and a sense of relatedness to others: identity achievement, interpersonal competence;

Team skills are shared qualities of the team that are instrumental to an effective team environment and overall team success: leadership, communication, cohesion, team confidence.

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